

TRAGIC FEATURES OF AMERICAN DREAM IN 'AN AMERICAN TRAGEDY' BY THEODORE DREISER

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Annotation: The article below sheds light on the tragedy genre in literature, Theodore Dreiser's contribution to American literature, his life and literary career, general data about 'An American Tragedy', main themes and moral of the novel, its role and impact in today's world as well. During the article, the analysis of the novel is given with clear explanations and details.

Key words: novel, style, death, wealth, social class, criminal, society, challenge.

Tragedy is a literary genre that has been present in literature for thousands of years. It is a form of drama that focuses on the downfall of a tragic hero or heroine, often due to their own fatal flaw or the actions of others. Tragedy typically ends in the death or destruction of the main character, leaving the audience with a sense of sadness and loss. Tragedy often explores themes of fate, free will, and the human condition. It can be a powerful tool for examining the darker aspects of human nature, such as greed, jealousy, and revenge. Tragic works often evoke strong emotions in readers or viewers, and can be a way to confront and process difficult or painful experiences. Some of the most famous examples of tragedy in literature include Shakespeare's plays such as Romeo and Juliet and Macbeth, as well as Greek tragedies like Oedipus Rex and Antigone. These works have endured for centuries because they speak to universal human experiences and emotions, and offer insights into the complexities of the human psyche. While tragedy can be a difficult genre to read or watch, it can also be cathartic and thought-provoking. It can help us to confront our own mortality and the fragility of life, and encourage us to reflect on our own actions and choices. Ultimately, tragedy reminds us of the

importance of empathy, compassion, and connection in a world that can often be cruel and unforgiving.

Theodore Dreiser was an American writer who made significant contributions to American literature in the early 20th century. His works often focused on the struggles of ordinary people, particularly those from working-class backgrounds, and explored themes of social inequality, capitalism, and the American dream. One of Dreiser's most famous works is *Sister Carrie*, a novel that tells the story of a young woman who moves to Chicago to pursue her dreams of becoming an actress. The novel explores the challenges she faces as a woman in a male-dominated society, and the compromises she must make to achieve success. Dreiser's other notable works include *An American Tragedy*, which tells the story of a young man who becomes embroiled in a murder case, and *The Financier*, which explores the world of high finance and corruption in early 20th century America. Dreiser's writing style was often criticized for being too blunt and unpolished, but his works were praised for their realism and their ability to capture the complexities of human nature. He was an important figure in the naturalist literary movement, which sought to portray life as it really is, without idealizing or romanticizing it. Dreiser's contributions to American literature helped to establish a new tradition of realism and social criticism in American fiction. His works continue to be studied and appreciated today for their insights into the American experience and their relevance to contemporary social issues. "An American Tragedy" is a novel written by Theodore Dreiser and published in 1925. The novel is loosely based on the real-life murder of Grace Brown by Chester Gillette in 1906, which took place in upstate New York. The novel tells the story of Clyde Griffiths, a young man from a poor family who dreams of achieving wealth and success. He becomes involved with two women, Roberta Alden and Sondra Finchley, but ultimately chooses to pursue a relationship with Sondra, a wealthy socialite. When Roberta becomes pregnant, Clyde tries to convince her to have an abortion, but she refuses. In a moment of desperation, Clyde takes Roberta out on a boat and drowns her. He is eventually caught and sentenced to death. "An American Tragedy" is considered a classic of

American literature and is known for its exploration of themes such as social class, ambition, and the corrupting influence of wealth. The novel has been adapted into several films and stage productions, including the 1951 film "A Place in the Sun" starring Elizabeth Taylor and Montgomery Clift.

The main topics of "An American Tragedy" include social class, ambition, love, and the corrupting influence of wealth. The novel explores the ways in which social class can limit opportunities and shape one's destiny, as well as the dangers of pursuing wealth and success at any cost. The moral of the novel is that the pursuit of wealth and success can lead to tragic consequences if it is not tempered by a sense of morality and responsibility. The novel suggests that true happiness and fulfillment come from living a life of integrity and compassion, rather than from material possessions or social status. Additionally, the novel highlights the importance of personal accountability and the consequences of one's actions. The American Dream is a concept that has been deeply ingrained in the American psyche for generations. It is the idea that through hard work, determination, and perseverance, anyone can achieve success and prosperity in the land of opportunity. However, Theodore Dreiser's novel "An American Tragedy" challenges this notion by exposing the tragic features of the American Dream. The novel tells the story of Clyde Griffiths, a young man from a poor family who dreams of achieving wealth and success. He moves to the city and lands a job at a prestigious hotel, where he meets and falls in love with a wealthy young woman named Sondra Finchley. Clyde becomes obsessed with Sondra and sees her as the key to his success and happiness. However, Clyde's ambition and desire for wealth lead him down a dark path. When he discovers that he has impregnated a poor factory worker named Roberta Alden, he becomes consumed with fear that she will ruin his chances with Sondra. In a moment of desperation, Clyde plots to murder Roberta by taking her out on a boating trip and drowning her. The tragic features of the American Dream are evident throughout the novel. Clyde's pursuit of wealth and success leads him to commit a heinous crime, all in the name of protecting his social status and reputation. He is so consumed with the idea of achieving his dreams that he is

willing to sacrifice everything, including his own morality and humanity. Furthermore, the novel highlights the limitations of social class and how it can shape one's destiny. Clyde is born into poverty and has limited opportunities for upward mobility. He sees wealth and success as the only way to escape his circumstances and achieve happiness. However, his obsession with these goals blinds him to the moral consequences of his actions. The corrupting influence of wealth is also a central theme in the novel. Clyde becomes so enamored with the lifestyle of the wealthy that he is willing to do anything to achieve it. He sees Sondra as the embodiment of everything he desires and is willing to sacrifice his own integrity to win her over. The tragic ending of the novel serves as a cautionary tale about the dangers of pursuing the American Dream at any cost. Clyde's actions ultimately lead to his downfall, and he is punished for his crimes. The novel suggests that true happiness and fulfillment come from living a life of integrity and compassion, rather than from material possessions or social status. "An American Tragedy" by Theodore Dreiser exposes the tragic features of the American Dream. The novel challenges the notion that success and prosperity can be achieved through hard work and determination alone. Instead, it suggests that the pursuit of wealth and success can lead to tragic consequences if it is not tempered by a sense of morality and responsibility. The novel serves as a cautionary tale about the dangers of sacrificing one's integrity and humanity in the pursuit of the American Dream.

"An American Tragedy" has had a significant impact on American literature and culture. The novel's exploration of the dark side of the American Dream challenged the optimistic view of success and prosperity that was prevalent in the early 20th century. It exposed the limitations of social class and the corrupting influence of wealth, themes that continue to resonate with readers today. The novel's portrayal of the criminal justice system also sparked important conversations about the fairness and effectiveness of the legal system. Dreiser's depiction of Clyde's trial and execution raised questions about the death penalty and the treatment of defendants in the criminal justice system. The novel has been

adapted into several films, including the Academy Award-winning "A Place in the Sun" (1951). Overall, "An American Tragedy" remains a powerful and thought-provoking work of literature that continues to challenge readers to consider the true nature of the American Dream and its impact on individuals and society.

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